

**On the path of recovering platinum-group metals and rhenium: a review on the recent advances
in secondary-source and waste materials processing**

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Abstract

Several economical and industrial applications related to environmental protection and energy conversion/storage have posed a high demand for platinum-group metals (PGMs) and Re. These materials are typically used in chemical, petroleum, refinery, and automotive catalysis applications, consequently leading to resource scarcity, despite the intensive efforts undertaken for environment protection. Hence, it is imperative to recirculate these rare metals *via* recovery and recycling. Moreover, the motivation behind such efforts is fuelled by the substantial gap between the supply, demand, and recycling of PGMs and the projected rapid depletion of Re resources. Thus, the recovery of PGMs and Re from waste and secondary sources is of paramount significance. Additionally, the criticality of these technologies strongly necessitates research on this subject. In this context, the present study aims to critically review the recent progress and advancements in effective recovery of PGMs and Re from materials relevant in sustainable technologies. Furthermore, the practical aspects, environmental impact, and issues related to the unit processes of PGM and Re recoveries are emphasised.

Keywords: PGMs; Catalysts; Superalloys; Recovery; Recycling; Waste Materials; Secondary Sources

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1. Introduction

Numerous industries rely on transition-group metals, among which Pt, Pd, Rh, Ru, Ir and Os—collectively referred to as platinum-group metals (PGMs)—and Re are of particular significance (Fogg and Cornellisson, 1993; Hagelüken, 2012a, 2012b; Kesieme et al., 2019; Rao and Reddi, 2000; Sowa et al., 2016; Werner et al., 2023). These metals are crucial in various energy conversion/storage processes and catalytic processes aimed at treating the exhaust gases of combustion chambers. In this context, PGMs and Re are widely applied, *i.e.*, as catalysts in energy-carrier processing, high-octane-petrol production, catalytic flue gas purification systems, and manufacturing of energy storage devices and efficient energy grids (Angelidis et al., 1999; Jafarifar et al., 2005; John, 2015). Such applications align with the efforts of the International Energy Agency in mitigating the current energy crisis; thus, PGMs and Re are strategic resources (Fogg and Cornellisson, 1993; International Energy Agency, n.d.; John, 2015; U.S. Department of Energy, 2022; Werner et al., 2023).

Platinum-group metals and Re are extremely important in catalytic processes. Related applications include automobile emission-control systems, fuel cells, and chemical syntheses (John, 2015). Platinum-group-metal catalysts help facilitate important reactions such as the conversion of harmful pollutants into less toxic substances, thus contributing to environmental sustainability. Additionally, PGMs, along with Re, are essential for high-octane-petrol production (Angelidis et al., 1999; Jafarifar et al., 2005; John, 2015). Further, these catalysts enable the conversion of low-octane feedstocks into high-performance petrol that can address the demands of modern engines while minimising the environmental impact.

Despite their importance, the abundance of these metals in the Earth's crust is extremely low. Compared to the concentration of O, Si, or Fe, which exceeds 50×10^6 parts per billion (ppb), the average concentrations of Rh, Ir, Os, and Re are only 0.5 ppb (Rudnick and Gao, 2003). All the PGMs and Re are considered as the rarest metals and are less abundant than Au, except for Ru (Haxel et al., 2002). The above-mentioned factors lead to a significant, persistent supply–demand gap of PGMs. This gap, together with the projected exhaustion of primary sources of Re and caution on near-depletion of mineable PGM supplies, has necessitated the development of effective recovery strategies (Gordon et al., 2006; Henckens et al., 2014; Johnson Matthey, 2022).

The supply–demand gap of PGMs and the impending depletion of primary sources of Re have highlighted the need for recovery strategies and alternative extraction methods. The development and implementation of sustainable practices in managing these metals are critical for addressing the challenges faced by the modern society and for ensuring a secure, resilient supply chain. In this context, the present review aims to organise PGM and Re recovery strategies, with a focus on technologies proven for real secondary-source sample materials or samples prepared to largely mimic the composition of real samples.

Although Re is not a PGM, the recovery of PGMs and Re have been collated as separate, successive sections because of the above-mentioned reasons and the need for combined usage of PGMs and Re, as mandated by certain technologies (Jafarifar et al., 2005). Moreover, this reasoning has been implemented to eliminate any misinterpretation of the distinction of these elements while retaining the commonalities and highlighting the synergies thereof.

2. Platinum-group Metals

Platinum-group metals are widely used in many industrial sectors; their popularity is attributed to their chemical inertness to various chemical reagents and their excellent catalytic properties (Fogg and Cornellisson, 1993). They are used in chemical, automotive, refining, glass, dentistry, electronic, electrical, photovoltaic, fuel cell, medicine, and pharmaceutical applications and as jewellery and capital goods (Hagelüken, 2012b; Rao and Reddi, 2000). Therefore, the ever-increasing demand for PGMs surpasses their supply. The global PGM market by weight and its evolution is shown in **Figure 1**. The figure illustrates that despite the efforts, the recovery of Pt, Pd, and Rh is not yet sustainably sufficient to address their supply–demand gap (Ueda et al., 2016). Currently, there is a PGM deficit, and their global reserves are decreasing (Johnson Matthey, 2022).

Figure 1. Global supply and recycling *versus* the demand of Pt, Pd, and Rh×5 in tons per annum. The graph was created based on the data collected from the reference (Johnson Matthey, 2022).

Waste catalysts used for chemical reactions are one of the most abundant secondary sources of PGMs. After many cycles of their operation and regeneration, PGM-based catalysts are deactivated, and they end up as a waste. Automotive catalytic converters are equally important as they have a much higher concentration of Pt, Pd, or Rh than the primary sources (Fogg and Cornellisson, 1993), thereby contributing to the recovery process. One automotive catalytic converter contains up to 2000 g t⁻¹ of PGMs in total, whereas a primary source of PGMs contains less than 10 g t⁻¹ of PGMs on average

(Hagelüken, 2012b). Other secondary sources from which the catalysts can be recovered include computer motherboards (approximately 80 g t^{-1} of Pd), mobile phones (up to 130 g t^{-1} of Pd), and jewellery (Hagelüken, 2012b). The ubiquitous use of PGMs has necessitated research on using road dust as a potential raw material (Taylor, 2011) with a PGM abundance of up to 2.25 g t^{-1} and 1 g t^{-1} for Pt and Pd, respectively (Jackson et al., 2007).

All the above-mentioned secondary materials typically have a higher concentration of PGMs and are more readily available than the natural resources (Fogg and Cornellison, 1993; Hagelüken, 2012b), rendering them a perfect choice for accessing PGMs. Thus, in 2014, recycling of spent automotive catalytic converters accounted for 60% of total Pt recovery (Ueda et al., 2016); however, only >5% of Pd and Ru used in electronic devices was recovered (Li and Song, 2016). The scientific community devotes much effort towards developing novel methods and techniques for effective PGM recovery to increase the efficiency and the overall quantity of recirculated PGMs, as reflected in the literature (Chen et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2015; Grilli et al., 2023; Iftekhar et al., 2022; Izatt et al., 2016; Karim and Ting, 2021; Sun et al., 2022; Ueda et al., 2016; Xia and Ghahreman, 2023; Yakoumis et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2021). This continuous growing interest in sourcing PGMs from secondary materials is attributed to the fact that despite scientific and technological efforts, the gap between the supply of the PGMs and their demand and recycling is significant, and the situation needs a substantial improvement (see **Figure 1** for details).

Platinum-group metals can be recovered using many methods, out of which the two main groups are as follows: hydrometallurgical methods and pyrometallurgical methods. Hydrometallurgical methods are based on the dissolution of PGMs from waste materials or on the dissolution of a carrier containing PGMs. Mixtures of acids and oxidisers, cyanides, and various additives are employed to achieve this effect (Angelidis, 2001; Bolinski and Distin, 1992; Dong et al., 2015; Harjanto et al., 2006; Meng and Han, 1995; Panda et al., 2018; Yoo, 1998). High recovery efficiencies can be reached, depending on the selected technique and its conditions. Pyrometallurgical methods involve different means of subjecting a secondary source of PGMs to thermal treatment in the presence of various additives. For example, in metal collection methods, a primary subcategory of pyrometallurgical methods, the PGM-bearing materials are heated to high temperatures, facilitating the transfer of PGMs to the collector metal phase and separating them from the slag-forming carriers (Dong et al., 2015). However, some techniques from both the groups may generate certain contaminants or hazardous compounds, thereby necessitating further steps to prevent environmental pollution (Jha et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2021; Voncken, 2019).

Other approaches for PGM recovery include methods using biological and organic matter or non-biological solid-state extraction techniques, such as molecular recognition technology (MRT) (Izatt et al., 2000) and ion-exchange resins, which can capture PGM ions from dilute solutions (Cyganowski and Dzimitrowicz, 2020). As per the related literature, although relatively high recovery yields can be achieved, the PGMs recovery efficiency needs to be increased further (Chen et al., 2021; Dong et al.,

2015; Iftekhhar et al., 2022; Jha et al., 2013; Karim and Ting, 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Nicol et al., 2021; Padamata et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2022; Yakoumis et al., 2021). In this context, the present work critically reviews the following: (i) recent progress in methods enabling the effective recovery of PGMs *via* hydrometallurgical, biometallurgical, and IX techniques, (ii) practical aspects and the potential of the above-mentioned technologies for industrial application, and (iii) actual impact of these technologies on the issues related to an increase in the global yield of recovered PGMs.

3. Hydrometallurgy for PGM recovery

The main operation mode of hydrometallurgical processes for PGM recovery is selective dissolution of a part of or the entire treated raw material by a chosen procedure. One method is the direct transfer of PGMs from a given raw material into a solution and etching it out; another method is the precipitation of the already dissolved PGMs. The precipitation can be conducted by forming complex compounds of PGMs under acidic or alkaline conditions in the presence of complexing agents (e.g. iodides, bromides, and chlorides) or additional compounds, elements, or ions (e.g. oxygen, iodine, chlorine, and hydrogen peroxide) (Angelidis, 2001; Bolinski and Distin, 1992; Dong et al., 2015; Harjanto et al., 2006; Meng and Han, 1995; Panda et al., 2018; Yoo, 1998).

The melting points of Pd, Pt and Rh with respect to the energies of their metallic bonds are 1552 °C, 1772 °C and 1966 °C, respectively (Mak et al., 2008). Their reactivity, in turn, decreases in that order; hence, Pd dust can be dissolved using concentrated HNO₃ or H₂SO₄, and Pt is soluble in *aqua regia* (HNO₃:HCl = 1:3 *mol/mol*) alone, but Rh cannot be dissolved (Chen and Huang, 2006). **Figure 2** schematises the pretreatment and general procedure in hydrometallurgy. However, each process included in this diagram can vary, depending on the type of the chosen hydrometallurgical treatment.

Figure 2. Schematic of the main processes in a hydrometallurgical method for PGM recovery (figure reproduced from the reference (Dong et al., 2015) with the permission of Elsevier).

3.1. Halo-complex formation

3.1.1 Chloro-complex formation

Platinum, palladium, and rhodium exhibit a high capability of forming halo-complexes in acidic solutions of halides (Harjanto et al., 2006). Platinum is mainly present in these solutions in the +2 and +4 oxidation states. In chloride solutions, Pt chloride complexes with coordination numbers of 4 and 6 are formed by the Pt(II) and Pt(IV) species, respectively. Palladium also exists in the +2 and +4 oxidation states; consequently, its chloride complexes have coordination numbers of 4 and 6, respectively. The most stable oxidation state of Rh is +3. Rhodium mostly forms complexing ions with the coordination number of 6.

The following half equations (1)–(3) show the formation reactions of chloride complexes of Pt, Pd, and Rh, respectively, and their corresponding electrochemical potentials (Bard et al., 2017; Harjanto et al., 2006; Haynes, 2014).

In the halogen-complexing method, the PGM-containing raw materials are etched in halide-ion-containing solutions, such as a HCl solution, together with oxidising agents such as HNO₃, Cl₂, NaClO₃, and H₂O₂ (de Sá Pinheiro et al., 2004; Grumett, 2003; Marinho et al., 2011; Paiva et al., 2022; Sun and Lee, 2011). When Cl is employed as the halogen of choice, the Cl₂ formed in the solution provides a high oxidation potential. Upon self-reduction, it is an abundant source of Cl⁻ ions as well. This process is described by the subsequent reactions (4)–(13) (Dong et al., 2015).

To achieve a relatively high PGM recovery efficiency, the raw material should preferably, or at times essentially, be pre-processed (Morcali, 2020; Xolo et al., 2021), as shown in **Figure 2**, because the PGMs present in the raw material constitute only a fraction of the total composition of the waste material (Gómez et al., 2002; Jimenez De Aberasturi et al., 2011; Leśniewska et al., 2004; Schäfer and Puchelt, 1998). Thus, certain auxiliary processes based on grinding, baking, reducing, or pressure etching of the raw material are required before the hydrometallurgical treatment. Moreover, these processes help to remove the organic-matter which exists as impurities in the raw material (Fornalczyk and Saternus, 2009; Jimenez De Aberasturi et al., 2011; Panda et al., 2018), thereby reducing the need for further treatment.

By decreasing the equilibrium potential and increasing the concentration of Cl⁻ ions, the leaching process can be abetted further, as pointed out by Ilyas et al. (2020), who extensively studied the effect of various factors such as temperature and pulp density on the leaching efficiency of PGMs. They reported that under optimal conditions, a HCl–H₂O₂ mixture led to 90% Pt recovery and 94% Pd recovery, upon transfer to a solution and subsequent precipitation using NH₄Cl.

The method proposed by Sakakibara et al. (1983) recovered 97% Pt and 81% Rh. Such efficiencies were achieved after the pre-treatment process, comprising the soaking of the raw material in a 2 mol L⁻¹

La(NO₃)₃ solution, followed by its roasting in air at 1200 °C. Next, the roasted raw material was reduced by NaBH₄. Then, the PGMs were transferred from the raw material to the solution using HCl and a mixture of oxidising reagents (Sakakibara et al., 1983). The researchers at The Mining and Materials Processing Institute of Japan (Harjanto et al., 2006) achieved 88%, 99%, and 77% recoveries of Pt, Pd, and Rh, respectively. Their method was based on facile one-step digestion, replacement of HCl by NaClO as the source of Cl⁻ ions, and addition of a little H₂O₂. Through this approach, a lower acidity of the solution was achieved while maintaining a high Pt solubility (Dong et al., 2015; Harjanto et al., 2006).

The use of a boiling solution of HCl and HNO₃ and the addition of AlCl₃ resulted in digestion efficiencies of 95% for Pt and 82% for Rh, along with a slight increase in the digestion efficiency of Rh when HCl was fully replaced with AlCl₃ (Bolinski and Distin, 1992). The complete replacement of HCl and HNO₃ by AlCl₃ and Al(NO₃)₃, respectively, was investigated by Forte et al. (2020). Their study was inspired by another study (Sare et al., 1973) in which the digestion rate of noble metals in concentrated solutions of AlCl₃ and Al(NO₃)₃ was significantly higher than that in *aqua regia*, achieving a 95% leaching efficiency for Pd in 15 min at a salt:catalyst ratio of 35 g g⁻¹ and T = 80 °C. After 4 h, leaching efficiency for Pt and Rh reached 64% and <20%.

Angelidis (2001) attempted to develop a hydrometallurgical method for Pt and Rh recovery on the laboratory scale, consequently establishing a four-step technique. The first step was reductive digestion in a solution of H₂SO₄ and N₂H₆SO₄, followed by oxidative digestion in a solution of HCl, AlCl₃, and NaClO. The third step was final digestion using a HCl solution; finally, the precipitate from the solution was extracted using a spinning Al rod and a Pb(CH₃COO)₂ additive. This method resulted in Pt and Rh recovery at an efficiency of ~95% and a rate (per unit surface area) of 3–30 mg h⁻¹ m⁻² with respect to the surface area of the raw-material (Angelidis, 2001).

Jafarifar et al. (2005) achieved 98% Pt recovery upon digesting a Pt–Re bearing spent-reforming catalytic material in *aqua regia* at a liquid:solid ratio of 2:5. Such a relatively high efficiency was reached because the leaching process was supported by a 150 W microwave radiation field. The concept of microwave-assisted digestion, allowing for higher recovery yields, developed gradually. Accordingly, Suoranta et al. (2015) achieved up to 100% leaching efficiency for Rh and >90% leaching efficiency for Pt and Pd in spent automotive catalysts soaked in HCl, HNO₃, or *aqua regia*. Their work employed cloud-point extraction as well (Hinze and Pramauro, 1993): a surfactant was added to the solution, leading to the capture of metal-ion complexes by the micelles. Temperature alterations resulted in phase separation, and the PGMs were dragged into the surfactant-rich phase and extracted efficiently.

Abo Atia et al. (2021) performed microwave-assisted chloride leaching of PGMs from a spent automotive catalyst using H₂O₂ instead of HNO₃ as the oxidizing agent. Their paper contributed to a better understanding of the chemical interactions, by which H₂O₂ facilitated halogen-complexing of PGMs and yielded leaching efficiencies of 98%, 94%, and ~90% for Pt, Pd, and 90%, respectively, depending on the system.

Trucillo et al. (2022) used a solution of H₂O₂ along with a relatively low-concentration HCl and assessed the impact of temperature, oxidiser concentration, and particle size of the raw material on the efficiency of PGM recovery. Samples of a spent automobile catalyst soaked in a H₂O₂ solution with a concentration of 0%–7% v/v were used for leaching Pt in a dilute HCl solution at 20 °C and 90 °C for 140 h. The respective leaching efficiencies were up to 96% and >99%.

Paiva et al. (2022) obtained similar results in their study on the effects of temperature, HCl concentration, particle size of the raw material, and liquid:solid ratio on PGM recovery efficiency. The following optimal conditions were established: 11.6 mol dm⁻³ HCl, 1% v/v H₂O₂, 60 °C, L/S ratio of 2 dm³ kg⁻¹, and 3 h of leaching, leading to a recovery of up to 98% of Pt, 99% of Pd, and up to 96% of Rh, depending on the treated secondary source material.

Extraction from solid or crushed secondary source material can be employed in the aqueous or organic phase. The omission of the water phase and formation of PGM complex directly in an organic phase can be considered the solvometallurgical aspect of metal processing (Binnemans and Jones, 2017). Nguyen et al. (2021) implemented this approach of non-aqueous solvent extraction by treating a spent automotive catalyst sample with solutions containing FeCl₃ or CuCl₂ as oxidising agents in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or acetonitrile (CH₃CN), enabling the transfer of PGMs into the solution. They proposed a procedure of solvo-leaching Pd first with 0.01 M FeCl₃/CH₃CN and then increasing the FeCl₃/CH₃CN concentration to leach Pt and Rh into another solution. The subsequent multi-stage scrubbing and stripping (see Section 3.3 - Techniques utilising solvent extraction and ionic liquids) enabled selective extraction of the PGMs from solutions. The methods of PGM recovery based on the formation of their respective chloro-complexes are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Summary of PGM recovery in HCl-based media via formation of chloro-complexes).

Technique	Recovery efficiency (%)			Source material	Reference
	Pt	Pd	Rh		
Initial treatment La(NO ₃) ₃	97	a	81	Rh-containing catalyst on an Al carrier	(Sakakibara et al., 1983)
AlCl ₃ addition	95	a	82	Spent honeycomb automotive catalyst	(Bolinski and Distin, 1992)
Microwave assistance	98	a	99 Re	Pt–Re bimetallic reforming catalyst	(Jafarifar et al., 2005)
Reduction, oxidation and final leaching, Al rod precipitation	95	a	95	Spent automotive catalyst	(Angelidis, 2001)
Substituting a part of HCl with NaClO	88	99	77	Automotive catalyst residue	(Harjanto et al., 2006)
Microwave assistance	>90	>90	>99	Recycled monolith automotive catalyst	(Suoranta et al., 2015)

Replacing AlCl ₃ by Al(NO ₃) ₃	64	95	<20	Spent automotive catalyst	(Forte et al., 2020)
H ₂ O ₂ as the oxidiser	90	94	a	Exhausted diesel oxidation catalyst	(Ilyas et al., 2020)
Microwave assistance	98	94	90	Various spent automotive catalysts, ground and mixed	(Abo Atia et al., 2021)
Solvometallurgy FeCl ₃ /CuCl ₂ in CH ₃ CN/DMSO ^b	>80	>99	>35	Various spent automotive catalysts, ground and mixed	(Nguyen et al., 2021)
H ₂ O ₂ as the oxidiser	98	99	96	Spent automotive catalysts with Pt, Rh/Pt, Pd, Rh	(Paiva et al., 2022)
H ₂ O ₂ as the oxidiser	>99	a	a	Unused alumina-wash-coated diesel catalyst	(Trucillo et al., 2022)

a. PGM unrecovered or not present in the study

b. Leaching efficiencies, the best results are shown

The process of using HCl/H₂O₂, along with microwave assistance, exhibits a trend with regard to the chloro-complexing of PGMs in raw materials. The popularity of acid etching as a method for recovering PGMs from secondary raw materials is mainly due to its simplicity and ease of use. Although the PGM recovery efficiency using this technology has increased over the years, high costs are still incurred because of potentially hazardous NO_x or Cl₂ and HClO emissions generated while using *aqua regia* (Jha et al., 2013; Voncken, 2019) or HClO/H₂O₂ (Abo Atia et al., 2021; Ilyas et al., 2020; Kudryashov et al., 2004), respectively, which must be eliminated. Another issue related to this technology is its poor selectivity (Abo Atia et al., 2021; Moleko-Boyce et al., 2022; Suoranta et al., 2015). Both the problems necessitate further developments to eliminate this bottleneck.

3.1.2 Iodo- and other halogen-complex formation

Hydrometallurgical recovery techniques for PGM have been studied using other halogens as well, albeit to a smaller extent than those on chloro-complex formation. Results from previous studies demonstrate that the most stable complexes of PGMs are formed with I₂ (Bard et al., 2017; Dawson and Kelsall, 2006; Trinh et al., 2020). Active iodide species such as I⁻, I₃⁻, and IO⁻ (Trinh et al., 2020; Zanjani and Baghalha, 2009) are formed, as described by reactions (14)–(17) (Bard et al., 2017; Ramette and Sandford, 1965; Trinh et al., 2020; Zanjani and Baghalha, 2009).

The dissolution of PGMs in solutions bearing I_3^- and I^- is described by reactions (18)–(21) (Dawson and Kelsall, 2013; Trinh et al., 2020).)

In the case of Pt, either the stable final product, *i.e.* the PtI_6^{2-} ions, or the intermediate PtI_4^{2-} ions are formed. The PtI_4^{2-} ions may be metastable, depending on the oxidant concentration, whose function is performed by the active I^- ions (Dawson and Kelsall, 2006).

Zanjani and Baghalha (2009) analysed the factors impacting the Pt extraction from a spent reforming catalyst and concluded that an increase in the temperature, pH, and liquid:solid ratio positively influenced the extraction kinetics. Meng and Han (1995) developed a method that allowed for >95% recovery of Pt and Pd under optimal conditions via solutions containing I_3^-/I^- and NH_4^+ salts in an autoclave. Although studies on PGM recovery have focussed on Pt, Pd, and Rh recovery, Ru, Ir, and Os belong to this group as well. Thus, Patel and Dawson (2015), along with others (Patel et al., 2014), explored the potential of Ru recovery from end-of-life fuel cells for the first time by applying an electrical current to a Ru-bearing material immersed in an aqueous solution of NaCl, NaBr, or KI (Patel et al., 2014). They further developed the technique of Pt recovery from fuel cells *via* chemical dissolution in a KI solution, achieving a PGM recovery efficiency of up to 99%, depending on the material source (Patel and Dawson, 2015).

The disparity between the number of studies reported on chloro-complexing and other halogen-complexing methods may be ascribed to the much lower driving force for the dissolution of PGMs in Br^- and I^- media than in Cl^- media (Bard et al., 2017), evaporation of I_2 and Br_2 (Zanjani and Baghalha, 2009), or the potential formation of insoluble products (Patel and Dawson, 2015). Furthermore, the leaching process using I_2 solutions is preferably conducted in an O_2 -purged environment, impeding practical implementation. Moreover, among the active species—HIO, IO^- , I^- , I_2 , and I_3^- —HIO and IO^- get converted into inactive IO_3^- and other highly oxidised iodine–oxygen forms (Bard et al., 2017; Zanjani and Baghalha, 2009).

3.2. Cyanide complex formation

The recovery of PGMs by complexation with cyanides (CN^-) is applied in chemical and metallurgical industries (Atkinson et al., 1992; Chen and Huang, 2006; Chen et al., 2021), owing to the stability of these complexes in alkaline solutions. The main mechanisms governing the digestion of

PGMs with CN^- ions are presented in reactions (22)–(26) (Bruckard et al., 1992; Dong et al., 2015; Panda et al., 2018).)

Transfer of PGMs to a solution:

Decomposition of HCN:

The formation of $[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$ is challenging, and only $[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ is expected to be obtained using the cyanidation techniques presented herein (Bruckard et al., 1992; Hancock et al., 1977). Reactions (22)–(24) are similar to the reaction of Au with CN^- ions. The reaction efficiency is presumably controlled by the chemical reaction on the Pt surface, similar to that occurring during the formation of Au-cyanide complexes (Wadsworth et al., 2000). The difference is that the metallic bonds of PGMs are stronger than those of Au, and there is a passivating oxide layer on the top. Therefore, the PGM extraction using CN^- is conducted under high-temperature and high-pressure conditions because the cyanide complexes of PGMs exhibit slow kinetics at the room temperature and atmospheric pressure (Chen and Huang, 2006).

A change in the parameters such as the reaction temperature, O_2 pressure, or initial NaCN concentration does not affect the order of cyanide etching of PGMs, which is as follows: $\text{Pd} > \text{Pt} > \text{Rh}$ (Huang, 2004). Cyanide etching requires special instrumentation and adequate facilities to manage the toxic waste generated during the process, which is a source of serious environmental problems (Dong et al., 2015; Panda et al., 2018).

The U.S. Bureau of Mines studied the solubilisation of Pt cyanides by etching a spent pellet and monolith catalysts twice with a 1% NaCN solution for 1 h at 160 °C. The efficiencies of recovery were 90% and ~85%, respectively; however, the addition of a third step necessitated the use of an autoclave (Atkinson et al., 1992; Kuczynski et al., 1992). Another process that achieved Pt recovery efficiency of 85% involved the use of a NaCN solution at a ratio of 2:1 with reference to the treated raw material, over a temperature range of 140–180 °C, with a pH range of 8-9, and a reaction time of 1 h (Shams, 2004).

Chen and Huang (2006) achieved recoveries of 95%–96%, 97%–98%, and 90%–92% for Pt, Pd, and Rh, respectively, from a raw material containing 1000–2000 g t^{-1} of PGMs. The raw material was pre-treated by grinding it to a particle size of 0.0074 mm, followed by pre-digestion with an alkaline solution to remove the carrier of PGMs in the raw material and purify them by separating the organic

impurities. The conditions required were as follows: a liquid:solid ratio of 4, temperature of 160 °C, pressure of 2 MPa, O₂ pressure of 1 MPa, and a duration of 2 h. The raw material was digested twice in a 10 g L⁻¹ NaCN solution (Chen and Huang, 2006). As shown in **Table 2**, the operational procedures of Kuczynski et al. (1992) and Chen and Huang (2006) are the most effective in terms of the recovery efficiency and versatility.

Table 2. Summary of the results of PGM recovery using cyano-complex formation.

Technique	Recovery efficiency (%)			Source material	Reference
	Pt	Pd	Rh		
Regular and autoclave-assisted extraction ^a	94	94	92	Automobile catalytic converter	(Atkinson et al., 1992)
Heat-assisted dissolution	85	b	b	Spent industrial dehydrogenation catalyst	(Shams, 2004)
Grinding to dust, leaching at a liquid:solid ratio of 4 ^a	96	97	92	Spent automobile catalyst	(Chen and Huang, 2006)

a. The best results are shown

b. PGM unrecovered or not present during the study

The implementation of cyanidation as a hydrometallurgical technique for the recovery of noble metals, including PGMs and Au, is emerging obsolete because of the relatively slow kinetics (Chen and Huang, 2006; Saguru et al., 2018), necessity of an autoclave to sustain harsh reaction conditions, and generation of some hazardous waste (Miralles et al., 2000; Redman and Santore, 2012). A recent study by Latyuk et al. (2022) involving PGM cyanidation as the extraction step is worth mentioning, although the process was not the focus of their study. Nevertheless, cyanidation is a common method on the industrial scale to extract PGMs from different primary sources (Chen and Huang, 2006). However, the extraction is accompanied by voluminous tailing storage pools filled with wastewater containing metal-cyanide complexes (Chen et al., 2017). Therefore, the conventional hydrometallurgical cyano-complex formation techniques are being superseded by biometallurgical processes, which involve the *in situ* generation and subsequent destruction of bio-cyanide lixivants by microbes (Ilyas et al., 2022). The topic of biometallurgy is focussed in depth in Section 3.5 Biometallurgy of the present review.

3.3. Techniques utilising solvent extraction and ionic liquids

The complexing in halogen- and cyano-based media largely enable mass transfer from the solid phase to the aqueous phase. This transfer affords solutions containing spent complexing agents and relevant complex ions of PGMs, which may be useful despite their not being in the pure metallic form (Wei et al., 2022) if further separated. Hydrometallurgical solvent extraction (SX) is one such separation

method, in which organic solvents are used for selectively recovering the PGMs from aqueous leaching media (Paiva et al., 2022) (see the schematic of this separation in **Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Schematic of solvent extraction for PGM recovery (Paiva, 2017).

Hydrometallurgical SX has been extensively studied using model solutions (Al-Bazi and Freiser, 1988; Alguacil et al., 1997; Hasegawa et al., 1991; Lee et al., 2008; Nguyen et al., 2016a, 2016b; Reddy et al., 2010); hence, it has been investigated for PGMs from chloride solutions in liquid media by leaching real PGM-bearing secondary-source materials. Ionic liquids (ILs) comprise a family of low-temperature melting salts, usually consisting of organic cations and organic or inorganic anions (Hussey, 2014); the operating mechanisms of ILs and ion-exchange materials are similar (Firmansyah et al., 2020). Ionic liquids have been used as media for capturing PGM-ligand-complexing ions from appropriate leachates. The efficiency of the subsequent stripping varies with the metal, depending on the compound used, its concentration, and its selectivity (Firmansyah et al., 2019). Techniques employing SX, as described below, are summarised in **Table 3**.

Firmansyah et al. (2019) used undiluted trioctyldecyl phosphonium chloride ($P_{8,8,8,12}Cl$), an organic IL (Adamová et al., 2011). The Pt and Pd extraction from the leachate was substantial (100%), along with >80% of Rh extracted. Stripping efficiencies of up to 82% for Pt in 5 M HNO_3 , 91% for Pd with 0.1 M $CS(NH_2)_2$ in 1 M HCl, and 82% for Rh in 5 M HCl were achieved (Firmansyah et al., 2019).

Rzelewska-Piekut et al. (2021) used 0.005 M trihexyl(tetradecyl)phosphonium chloride (Cyphos® IL 101) in a toluene solution as the IL extractant, resulting in a Pt extraction efficiency of 100%; however, the use of 1 M HNO_3 as the stripping agent yielded a Pt stripping efficiency of merely 19%. In another study (Wiecka et al., 2022), a series of leaching processes in various combinations of organic and inorganic acids, followed by two extraction cycles with two 0.005 M toluene solutions containing either Cyphos® IL 101 or trihexyl(tetradecyl)phosphonium *bis*(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinate (Cyphos® IL 104), were performed. The first extraction achieved mid-80% to 100% efficiency for Pt and Pd, depending on the leachate, whereas the total extraction efficiency after the second extraction reached 100% for Pt and Pd in nearly every case. Two-step stripping was implemented; first with a

solution of 0.1 M thiourea in 0.5 M HCl yielding 100% stripping efficiency of Pd; next with a 3 M HCl solution resulting in 33% stripping efficiency of Pt. In addition to Pd, 87% of Fe present in the treated material was recovered, and apart from Pt, 100% of Zn was stripped, necessitating an additional purification step (Wiecka et al., 2022).

After the leaching process (described in Section 3.1. Halogen complex formation), Paiva et al. (2022) performed SX, using tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO), trihexyl(tetradecyl)phosphonium chloride (Cyphos® IL 101), and tri-*iso*-butylphosphine sulfide (Cyanex® 471X) solutions in toluene to treat the aqueous PGM-bearing phase. Cyphos® IL 101 could extract up to 100% Pt for a solution without Pd, and 99% Pt and 100% Pd, together with up to 9% Rh, 5% Nd, and quantitative amounts of Fe and Zn. Selectiveness of Pd *versus* Pt was exhibited in the case of Cyanex® 471X extraction because only Pd, Rh, and Fe (100%, 4%, and 99% respectively) were transferred from the leachate to the organic phase. Further, their work necessitated improved base-metal scrubbing agents and enhanced stripping techniques because despite the combination of extraction/scrubbing/stripping steps, only Pd was selectively obtained by stripping with thiourea in HCl, yielding 46% efficiency.

The solvometallurgical process proposed by Nguyen et al. (2021), started with the formation of chloro-complexes of PGM (see 3.1 Halogen complex formation). The PGMs in leachate were selectively extracted from one organic phase to another, in which Aliquat 336 ([A366][Cl]), a commercial mixture of quaternary ammonium salts in *p*-cymene was employed to effectively separate Pt from Rh. Yamada et al. (2023) synthesised pincer-shaped dithiophenol-based extractants, which harnessed the high affinity of S towards Pd(II), thereby forming coordination bonds between S and Pd(II) and consequently capturing Pd(II) from the aqueous phase into the phase of the extractant. In the experiments on a real leachate from a spent automotive catalyst, quantitative extraction was achieved with a 6 mM extractant solution, followed by water scrubbing and Pd(II) stripping in a thiourea solution, resulting in 100% efficiency.

In addition, Chen et al. (2017) devised the technique of Pt(II) and Pd(II) recovery from alkaline CN⁻ liquors, such as wastewater originating from the mining industry, using cyano-complexing *via* SX with phenoxyethyl dimethyl palmitylammonium bromide (PDPB), followed by the first stripping with a NH₄SCN solution and the second stripping with a thiodiglycol solution. The PDPB SX allowed for >98% extraction of both Pt(II) and Pd(II); >98% of Pd(II) was selectively stripped from the organic phase with the NH₄SCN solution, whereas >97% of Pt(II) was recovered during the second stripping using thiodiglycol. According to their study, the organic phase could be reused after stripping for at least six times, thereby reducing waste generation.

Ilyas et al. (2022) used Cyphos® IL 101, by which the PGMs were mobilised by the biogenic cyanide leaching medium (see 3.5. Biometallurgy) to capture the desired metals from the aqueous phase. They reported >96% Pt and Pd extraction efficiency, along with the selective stripping using NH₄SCN and thiodiglycol.

The results, collated in **Table 3**, demonstrate promising developments in the field of PGM recovery from waste materials. Depending on the technique chosen, the yield and the selectivity of the process may be high (Firmansyah et al., 2019; Yamada et al., 2023), which is the main goal of successful recovery. Currently, most reserachers have successfully recovered Pt and Pd; however, the potential towards Rh recovery by processes including SX has been exhibited only by Firmansyah et al. (2019).

Table 3. Summary of results of PGM recovery using methods employing solvent extraction.

Technique	Extraction/stripping efficiencies (%)			Source material	Reference
	Pt	Pd	Rh		
PDPB SX, ammonium thiocyanate, thiodiglycol stripping	99 / 98	99 / 98	a	Post-Pt–Pd-flotation cyanide leaching liquor from a mine	(Chen et al., 2017)
(P _{8,8,8,12} Cl) IL SX, HNO ₃ , CS(NH ₂) ₂ in HCl, HCl stripping	100 / 82	100 / 91	>80 / 82	Spent automotive catalyst	(Firmansyah et al., 2019)
Cyphos® IL 101 SX, HNO ₃ stripping	100 / 19	a	a	Spent automotive catalyst	(Rzelewska-Piekut et al., 2021)
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i> , Cyphos® IL 101 SX, ammonium thiocyanate, thiodiglycol stripping	>96 / >98	>96 / >94	a	Spent automotive catalyst	(Ilyas et al., 2022)
TOPO, Cyphos® IL 101, Cyanex® 471X SX, thiourea in HCl, malonic acid, NH _{3(aq)} stripping ^a	100 / 16	100 / 46	9 / a	Spent automotive catalysts with Pt, Rh / Pt, Pd, Rh	(Paiva et al., 2022)
Cyphos® IL 101, Cyphos® IL 104 2x SX, thiourea, HCl stripping ^b	100 / 33	100 / 100	a	Spent automotive catalyst	(Wiecka et al., 2022)
SX with dithiophenold-based extractants, thiourea stripping ^b	a	100 / 100	a	Leach liquor of spent automotive catalyst	(Yamada et al., 2023)

a. PGM unrecovered or not present during the study

b. The best results are shown

The described procedures involving SX focus on recovering the elements from acidic HCl solutions, in line with the current hydrometallurgical trends; extraction from alkaline-environment has also been examined (Bahaloo-Horeh and Mousavi, 2022a; Chen et al., 2017; Ilyas et al., 2022). The solvents used in the studies are mostly stable, with their flash points above 100 °C and boiling points above 150 °C, and non-carcinogenic (Firmansyah et al., 2019; Saguru et al., 2018). Further, as the organic phase is not spent during the extraction, that is, it retains its extractive properties after stripping, its recycling has been considered (Chen et al., 2017; Ilyas et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2021), thereby improving the ecological value of SX. Any solvent that might have vaporised could also be captured and recirculated;

however, solvent volatility is a major concern as 50% of the post-treatment greenhouse gas emissions is attributed to the solvents (Firmansyah et al., 2019; Hallett and Welton, 2011). Another environmental problem is their mixing with oxidants and acids, which may produce CO, CO₂, NO_x, and gaseous HCl (Saguru et al., 2018; Trinh et al., 2020). This issue entails the use of air-scrubbing equipment or reduction of the acidity of the PGM-bearing phase, up to the point of non-usage of acids, such as in the case of solvometallurgy (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Thus, ILs have been devised as low-vapour-pressure, non-flammable substitutes for regular solvents, affording a superior thermal/chemical/electrochemical stability, stronger potential for regeneration and recirculation, and considerably greener solvents (Hallett and Welton, 2011; Park et al., 2014). Their valuable attributes include resistance to highly acidic conditions, potential for improved selectiveness of PGM extraction over organic solvents, and high capacity (Berton et al., 2016; Park et al., 2014). The possibility of planting an IL onto a solid phase is another advantage, leading to an effective synthesis of materials with IX properties (Cochechi et al., 2022). Ionic liquids possess certain properties different from common solvents, such as high electrical conductivity and poor miscibility with supercritical CO₂, thereby allowing for a possible improvement on the sustainability front (Berton et al., 2016; Blanchard et al., 1999). Direct electrochemical deposition of the separated components as solid products would allow for skipping the stripping step (see **Figure 3** for details), whereas supercritical CO₂ could be used instead of currently employed acid stripping or complexing agents in SX, such as ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (Berton et al., 2016). However, replacing organic solvents with ILs in existing installations may be arduous, if not extremely difficult. High cost of IL production, generally high viscosity, and increased chemical complexity of the process reduce the overall industrial potential, which must be studied as the focal points (Makanyire et al., 2016). Although ILs are considered green owing to their reusability and potentially improved sustainability, they are regarded non-green as well because of their high toxicity, high cost, and difficulties in usage (Berton et al., 2016). These statements hold true if ILs were to simply replace SX in current unsustainable, open-looped technologies. However, the entire process would need to be remodelled around sustainability.

3.4. Carrier dissolution techniques

Carrier dissolution is not a recovery method but an approach to concentrate PGMs to increase the efficiency of the subsequent process steps, as shown in **Figure 2**. The alumina based Pt–Re/ γ -Al₂O₃-, Pt–Sn/ γ -Al₂O₃-, and Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃-type catalysts can be dissolved with an acidic or basic solution owing to the amphoteric nature of Al₂O₃ (Dong et al., 2015). Platinum-group metals would mostly remain in the solution in the metallic form, and the fraction that dissolves can be precipitated by cementation using Al powder as the reducing agent (Kim et al., 2010). Mishra (1987) etched γ -Al₂O₃ in automotive catalytic converters under pressure.

Dissolution of Al₂O₃ in alkaline solutions is performed in accordance with the Bayer's process (Hind et al., 1999). While γ -Al₂O₃ is dissolved in a NaOH or KOH solution, the PGM oxides concentrate

in the remaining precipitate. The solution, which is already devoid of PGMs, can be further refined to recover Al. These methods are useful only for the treatment of PGM-bearing raw materials on an Al support. In practice, they are used in plants such as Gemini Industries Inc., Heraeus Metal Processing Inc., Engelhard Chemicals, Nikki Universal, and Hindustan Platinum (Dong et al., 2015).

3.5. Biometallurgy

Biometallurgical methods are among the actively growing groups of PGM recovery techniques, *e.g.* utilisation of organic matter for biosorption, bioleaching, and bioreduction (Das, 2010; De Windt et al., 2005; Ng et al., 2013; Yakoumis et al., 2021). The mechanism of biosorption of metal ions is a complex process that depends on many factors such as the state of matter—animate (*e.g.* live bacteria) or inanimate,—type of organic matter, and the environment type in which the reaction occurs.

Typically, the mechanism of biosorption is based on the physical and chemical interactions between the metal ions and the functional groups present on the surface of the organic matter, such as electrostatic interactions, ion exchange, complexation, and chelation of metal ions (Özer et al., 2005). Therefore, the biosorption of PGMs on organic matter can be categorized as either physisorption or chemisorption. Bioleaching is schematised in **Figure 4**.

The association of Pt and Pd with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was reported by Godlewska-Żyłkiewicz and Kozłowska (2005). The immobilised bacteria *Chlorella vulgaris* were also studied as a biosorbent of Pt and Pd (Dziwulska et al., 2004). Ma et al. (2006) investigated the adsorption of Pt and Pd on bayberry tannins immobilised on the collagen fibre (BTICF) and reported adsorption efficiencies of 41.7 mg g⁻¹ and 27.5 mg g⁻¹ for Pt(IV) and Pd(II), respectively. Fujiwara et al. (2007) obtained a maximum adsorption capacity of 129.3 mg g⁻¹ of Pt(IV) and 109.5 mg g⁻¹ of Pd(II) in their samples, using a cross-linked chitosan resin modified with L-lysine as the adsorbent (Fujiwara et al., 2007).

Won et al. (2009) conducted Pt sorption from wastewater collected from an industrial laboratory on polyethyleneimine-modified deactivated *Escherichia coli* biomass and reported Pt recovery. At 108.8 mg g⁻¹ of the modified sorbent, a four-fold improvement of Pt sorption was observed over the result of 21.4 mg g⁻¹ of raw biomass.

Figure 4. Schematic scheme of PGM recovery by bioleaching (Yakoumis et al., 2021).

Chand et al. (2009) studied the adsorption capacity of barley straw carbon and obtained recoveries of 0.39 mmol kg⁻¹ and 0.64 mmol kg⁻¹ of sorbent for Pt(VI) and Pd(II), respectively. As shown by Akiba et al. (2022), Kraft lignin selectively adsorbed PGMs from a multi-metal ion solution with over 90% efficiency, exhibiting further catalytic potential. Their study demonstrated the possibility of Ru recovery, which is also a PGM, although it is not the primary focus of PGM recovery efforts.

Bioreduction of metals is a technique in which dissimilatory reducing bacteria use various metals or metalloids as terminal electron receptors for anaerobic respiration (Ng et al., 2013). *Shewanella oneidensis* was used for reducing and depositing Pd(II) onto Pd⁰ nanoparticles (NPs) by De Windt et al. (2005); subsequently, they enhanced the control over size and catalytic activity of the formed Pd⁰ NPs (De Windt et al., 2006). This technique can be employed to prepare ready-to-use catalysts or regenerate existing catalytic reactor beds, eliminating the need for emptying the reactor column of the packing.

Phytomining is another pathway for PGM recovery from unconventional sources such as urban soils collected 0.5 m away from a street, which may contain up to 60 mg t⁻¹ of Pt, over 75 mg t⁻¹ of Pd, and >50% road dust (Gawroński et al., 2022). Gawroński et al. (2022) and Masinire et al. (2022) have conducted research on determining potential of plants for PGM uptake.

In situ production of chemicals by microorganisms has been studied for potential usage. Ilyas and Kim (2022), along with others (Ilyas et al., 2022), used *Chromobacterium violaceum* to generate cyanide as a lixiviant medium to dissolve >90% of Pt and Pd from a secondary source of PGMs in an autoclave. Using *Aspergillus niger* fungi, Bahaloo-Horeh and Mousavi (2022b) obtained 60.9% and 73.3% extraction efficiencies for Pt and Pd, respectively. However, this technique is more of an enrichment technique than a recovery technique owing to the large quantities of other co-extracted metals. The

results of the above-mentioned studies are summarised in **Table 4**, and the collected data illustrate that organic materials can be harnessed as an alternative method for recovering PGMs from waste materials.

Table 4. Summary of results of PGM recovery using biometallurgical methods.

Technique	Recovery units	PGM sorption or recovery			Source material	Reference
		Pt	Pd	Rh		
Bayberry-tannin-immobilised collagen fibre membrane	mg g ⁻¹	41.7	27.5	a	Mg(II), Zn(II), Cu(II), Pt(IV), and Pd(II) solution	(Ma et al., 2006)
L-lysine-modified cross-linked chitosan resin ^b	mg g ⁻¹	129.3	109.5	a	Pt(IV) and Pd(II) analytical solutions	(Fujiwara et al., 2007)
Polyethylamine-modified <i>Escherichia coli</i>	mg g ⁻¹	108.8	a	a	Pt-containing inductively coupled plasma wastewater	(Won et al., 2009)
Barley straw carbon	mg g ⁻¹	76.1	66.0	a	Industrial HCl solution of Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Pd(II), and Au(III) with Pt(II) added	(Chand et al., 2009)
Kraft lignin	mg g ⁻¹	>0.4	>0.4	>0.4 Ru	Au(III), Ru(III), Pt(IV), and Pd(II) solution	(Akiba et al., 2022)
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	%	61	73	a	Spent monolith automobile catalyst	(Bahaloo-Horeh and Mousavi, 2022b)
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>	%	>95	>95	a	Spent automotive catalyst	(Ilyas et al., 2022)
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>	%	>95	>95	>90	Spent automotive catalyst	(Ilyas and Kim, 2022)

a. PGM unrecovered or not present during study

b. Technique not tested on a secondary-source material or a mixed-metal solution

3.6. Non-biological solid-phase extraction techniques

The processes described thus far in this review revolve around mass transfer into a liquid phase, precipitation, or adsorption on biological materials. Another distinct class of PGM recovery techniques involves capturing the material by a non-biological solid phase, such as IX resins, metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), and other materials that can adsorb PGMs *via* IX, complexation, ionic interactions, or electrostatic forces.

3.6.1 Ion-exchange- and metal–organic-framework-based techniques

Ion-exchange processes are considered an effective method for PGM recovery. They are based on the reversible exchange of ions between the solid and liquid phases, which occurs in two steps, namely, adsorption and elution. The adsorption stage is responsible for the extracting the ions of the desired PGMs, whereas the elution stage is related to the recovery, release of the adsorbed ions, and reuse of the resin.

The main features of ion-exchange resins are their high capacity, mechanical stability and exchange ratio and the ability to capture even a microscopic amount of the desired elements from a largely contaminated solution, rendering them suitable for highly dilute environments (Barbara and Liguori,

2009; Cyganowski and Dzimitrowicz, 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Nikoloski and Ang, 2014). The ion-exchange mechanism is presented in reaction (27) (Nikoloski and Ang, 2014).)

Here, M represents Pt, Pd, or Rh; B denotes an organic base; n = 2 (Pt and Pd) or 3 (Rh); and m = 6 (Pt and Rh) or 4 (Pd) (Lee et al., 2020; Nikoloski and Ang, 2014). The chloro-complexes of PGM tend to form ion-pairs with the chelating anion exchangers according to the following rule descending strength of the ion-pair: $[MCl_6]^{2-} > [MCl_4]^{2-} \gg [MCl_6]^{3-} >$ aqueous entities. This series determines the charge-to-size ratio or the charge density of the compound (Nikoloski and Ang, 2014).

In the method described by Cyganowski et al. (2020, 2019b, 2018), PGM extraction with an ion-exchange resin was used for the *in situ* production of a nanocomposite catalyst towards reducing 4-nitrophenol. Lee et al. (2020) presented an extensive review of functional-group-activated ion-exchange resins and their combinations with solvents. The methods described therein enable selective extraction of the desired PGMs from aqueous solutions, followed by their selective elution.

Chen et al. (2021) studied Zr-based MOFs functionalised with quaternary ammonium ligands to obtain a high-surface-area metal–organic resin, which could efficiently remove Pt and Pd cyanide complexes from alkaline wastewater. The optimal conditions and three adsorption–desorption cycles allowed for >90% PGM recovery. Li et al. (2022) examined MOFs and developed a one-step capture-to-catalyst technique using the MOFs assisted by ultrasonication in an alcoholic solvent, allowing for selective Pd(II) capture and its conversion into Pd NPs.

The Mg₃Al layered double hydroxide functionalised with methyltrialkylammonium chloride IL was examined by Coheci et al. (2022) for recovering Pd from aqueous solutions. The maximum Pd adsorption capacity reached 277.8 mg g⁻¹, using the co-synthesis functionalization method. Song et al. (2022) synthesised covalent isothiocyanurate frameworks with a maximum Pd uptake of 909 mg g⁻¹ maximum, which could function in highly acidic wastewater conditions. The reduction of captured Pd within the framework afforded a heterogenous catalyst for the Suzuki–Miyaura cross-coupling reaction (Song et al., 2022), which when harnessed could transform waste into a useful product.

3.6.2 Molecular recognition technology (MRT)

The formation of PGM complexes described in Sections 3.1 (halide complexes) and 3.2 (cyanide complexes) is the backbone of previously described separation techniques. However, these methods necessitate either subsequent or prior purification steps for the isolation of PGM. The developments by Pedersen (1967a, 1967b) on macrocyclic polyethers with a structure-specific host–guest chemistry, referred to as crown ethers (Pedersen, 1967b), and their complexes with metal salts yielded him a shared 1987 Nobel Prize in Chemistry (Izatt, 2007). The strong coordination between the crown ethers and alkali-metal cations is largely dependent on the ratio between the diameter of the cavity and the ionic diameter of the cation of a given polyether. Owing to steric hindrance, the cation must fit into the cavity

to form a stable complex; the closer the diameters, the more stable the complex, thereby favouring its formation (Lamb et al., 1979; Pedersen, 1967b). Other factors influencing the cation selectivity include the type and charge of cation, number of donor atoms, ring substitutions, and solvent type (Lamb et al., 1979).

Since the discovery of crown compounds, the first macrocyclic complexing agents, named cryptands, were synthesised by Dietrich et al. (1969), possessing two nitrogen atoms instead of oxygen that serve as bridgeheads. Macrocyclic compounds with either a part or all of the oxygen donor atoms replaced by nitrogen, sulfur, or phosphorus have also been synthesised, affecting the targeted ions (Bradshaw, 1978; Izatt et al., 1985; Lamb et al., 1979; Pedersen, 1978). Izatt and Bradshaw, along with others (Bradshaw et al., 1990, 1988; Bruening et al., 1995; Izatt, 2007, 1997; Tarbet et al., 1991), incorporated these macrocyclic compounds first into a liquid membrane and then onto silica gel, forming materials for rapid, solid-phase-selective cation separation. Consequently, these materials, together with their free-floating counterparts, emerged as the foundation of molecular recognition technology (MRT), which comprises four system-cycle steps: loading of the metal ions from a solution onto an appropriately functionalised support material, pre-elution wash to cleanse the column of the remaining solution, elution of the metal ions with a little eluent, and post-elution wash (Izatt, 2015; Izatt et al., 2015).

Products based on MRT have been successfully commercialised under the trademarks of SuperLig[®] and AnaLig[®] (Izatt et al., 2000) and have been widely industrialised, with plants of major metal refiners such as Impala Platinum employing this technology (Izatt et al., 2015, 2012, 2000). Owing to its ability to separate only the desired element from an assorted solution, MRT has a high potential for effective PGM recovery (Izatt et al., 2016) and is being extensively implemented by various PGM refiners (Izatt et al., 2012), with the new PGM recycling facilities employing MRT being under construction (IBC Advanced Technologies Inc., 2021).

4. Rhenium

Rhenium finds application in advanced industries owing to its properties such as high Young's modulus, tensile strength and hardness and ultra-high melting and boiling points. It is indispensable in the production of superalloys, which are used to construct the covers of space vehicles, probes, rockets, and supersonic aircraft turbines (Izatt et al., 2014; John, 2015; Sowa et al., 2016; Wang and Wang, 2018). Further, Re and these superalloys find application in energy-management-related processes. Rhenium is a prospective material for fabricating new-generation batteries (Wu et al., 2019), supercapacitors (Pazhamalai et al., 2020), and hydrogen-production catalysts (Ramírez et al., 2023). In this context, Re exhibits an exceptional catalytic activity over a wide temperature range (John, 2015; Sowa et al., 2016; Wang and Wang, 2018); hence, it is used along with PGMs as a catalyst for the production of high-octane-petrol and in energy-carrier conversion (Jafarifar et al., 2005; John, 2015). Since the applications of PGMs and Re concur in these processes, the analysis of PGM recovery from secondary sources benefits from considering Re within the scope. In this context, owing to its key importance in the refining

industry and in the manufacturing of fourth, fifth, and sixth generation of superalloys, Re is a strategic raw material (John, 2015; Kesime et al., 2019; Sowa et al., 2016; Wang and Wang, 2018), and these are the reasons for the great demand for this element (Angelidis et al., 1999; Sowa et al., 2016). **Figure 5** illustrates the global Re market. Based on the data, although the present demand apparently matches the supply, and current recycling measures ensure sufficient Re in the market, studies predict that the primary sources of Re will be exhausted around 2130, deeming the element scarce and necessitating recycling, similar to the case of PGMs (Henckens et al., 2014; Polyak, 2009).

There is no natural deposit of Re. It is produced worldwide as a by-product of Mo–Cu ores, polymetallic U ores, and Pt–Ni ores, serving as the primary sources. Its major producers from raw materials are Chile, Poland, and the United States (Izatt et al., 2014; John, 2015; Kesime et al., 2019; Polyak, 2009). All of these raw materials contain only a trace amount of Re (Kesime et al., 2019) that is recovered from post-production residues of copper, *i.e.* from waste sulfuric acid (Chanturiya et al., 2023). Moreover, 9 t of Re was produced in the USA in 2022, which was not sufficient to meet the demand. Between 2018 and 2022, up to >80% of Re consumed in USA must have been imported (Polyak, 2009). Its scarcity is a global issue because in general, developed economies that implement progressive technologies need Re. This situation poses a serious challenge with the rapid depletion of Re sources. Further, complex supply chains and lack of substituents for Re render the recovery techniques strategic (Kesime et al., 2019; Wang and Wang, 2018; Werner et al., 2023).

Fortunately, Re exhibits a high potential for recyclability (Henckens et al., 2019). Recycling materials that contain Re are mainly spent Pt–Re catalysts, overworked turbine blades of aircraft engines, scrap of Mo–Re and W–Re alloys, and scrap of Ni-based superalloys, which until recently were considered useless (Chanturiya et al., 2023). Spent Re scrap, including spent Re alloys and catalysts, contain more Re than natural raw materials. For instance, Ni–Re superalloys contain 1–20 wt.% Re; W–Re and Mo–Re superalloys contain 3–5 wt.% Re; and spent Re-containing catalysts consist of ~0.3 wt.% Re (Chanturiya et al., 2023). According to industrial sources, ~25 t of Re is presently recovered from waste worldwide, whose sources are mainly scrap Ni–Re superalloys and spent petroleum refining catalysts (Pt–Re bimetallic oil-reforming catalyst) (Shen et al., 2021). Besides a few reserach papers, reviews, and general information, the industrial production details of Re are confidential and are reported sparingly (Shen et al., 2021). In this context and in the purview of the industrial importance of Re, much effort is needed to preserve Re and render recovery strategies ready to persist with the projected approach of depletion of its sources.

*Global recycling data not available.

^eValues estimated based on the US apparent demand being 85% of the global apparent demand in the previous years.

Figure 5. Global supply and recycling *versus* the demand of Re in tons per annum. The graph was plotted based on the data collected from reference (Polyak, 2009).

5. Hydrometallurgy for Re recovery

In general, recycling of Re is a multi-stage process that combines pyro- and hydrometallurgical techniques, aimed at recovering Re in the form of ammonium perrhenate(VII) (NH_4ReO_4). This chemical may be further used as received or transformed into metallic Re by hydrogen reduction and vacuum sintering unit operations (Shen et al., 2021). **Figure 6** shows the technological diagram (flowsheet) of Re extraction and recycling from primary and secondary sources. After sintering, Re is usually extracted by dissolution of Re-bearing sources using sulfuric or nitric acid (Shen et al., 2021). Then, the Re-containing solutions are processed and subjected to various separation processes such as adsorption, liquid–liquid-liquid extraction or SX, ion exchange, membrane techniques, and chemical precipitation (Chanturiya et al., 2023; Shen et al., 2021).

Figure 6. Technological diagram (flowsheet) of Re extraction and recycling. Figure reproduced from the reference (Shen et al., 2021) with the permission of Elsevier.

Most Re deposits in Cu and Mo ores occur as ReS_2 with a low concentration of 0.2%, and the Re recovery therefrom is performed within unit processes represented in reactions (28)–(31) (Shen et al., 2021):

In the pyrometallurgical process of roasting copper concentrates, ReS_2 is oxidised to volatile rhenium heptoxide (Re_2O_7), which can then be recovered from acid wastewater as perrhenic acid (HReO_4) because of its solubility in water (Eqs. 28, 29). Then, irrespective of the applied technology, the hydrometallurgy for Re separation and recovery must focus on the ReO_4^- formed in the acidic media (Eq. 30). At this stage, owing to the low concentration of Re in solutions (2–30 mg L^{-1}) and large quantities of impurities, the SX process is often complicated and further poses a risk of additional contamination, which may not be sustainable. Therefore, ion exchange over solid ion-exchange resins is currently the only viable approach for affording effective and sustainable Re recovery (Eq. 31) (Shen et al., 2021).

In this context, the present work focusses on ion-exchange approaches implemented in recent large-scale technologies. There are limited reports on such approaches, often outside the scientific literature. In particular, MRT (described in Section 3.6. Non-biological solid-phase extraction techniques) could

also be employed for Re recovery (Izatt et al., 2012). The universality of these technologies is a strong motivation behind this review. Accordingly, the technologies could be easily extended to the processing of secondary sources, for which strategic improvements are highly instrumental.

5.1. Existing ion-exchange technologies

As mentioned in section 5, there are limited industrial reports on Re recovery and a few recent reports on the advances in the field. In general, the main problem with Re recovery is its low concentration and interference with other ions in the process solutions derived from secondary sources. These include especially Mo and W ions. These metals are present in process solutions in the form of their oxyanions— ReO_4^- , MoO_4^{2-} , and WO_4^{2-} —and may also exist as iso- or hetero-polyanions. They exhibit very similar chemical behaviours in aqueous solutions; hence, it is difficult to separate them economically. Therefore, dynamic development of ion-exchange technology has a strong motivation as this method can be easily applied to secondary sources of Re. In this context, a suitable ion-exchange technology will afford major advantages over other techniques (Mikahaylenko and Blokhin, 2012).

Molybdenum and tungsten tend to form large polymeric anions. Their size and efficiency of polymerisation depend on the pH and concentration of the solution. At $\text{pH} > 7$, Mo exists as the monomeric molybdate anion MoO_4^{2-} , whereas at $2 < \text{pH} < 6$, it exists in a polymerised form such as $\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}^{4-}$. At $\text{pH} < 2$, the cations MoO_2^{2+} , $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5^{2+}$, and $\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_8^{2+}$ are present. Tungsten may be present as WO_4^{2-} at $\text{pH} > 8$; as $\text{W}_7\text{O}_{24}^{6-}$, $\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{42}^{10-}$, $\text{H}_3\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{42}^{9-}$, and $\text{H}_4\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{42}^{8-}$ at $4 < \text{pH} < 6$; and as $\text{H}_2\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{6-}$ and $\text{H}_3\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ at $\text{pH} < 4$. Stronger acidification leads to further protonation and formation of larger neutral molecules such as $\text{H}_{12}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{42}$ that are poorly soluble and exist at $\text{pH} < 2$. In this context, Re(VII) has a stable form of ReO_4^- over the entire pH range (Pope, 1980), allowing for its selective recovery under ion-exchange conditions on polymer based ion-exchange resins, which requires a properly designed polymer.

Many thematic studies have been conducted on the selection of appropriate and selective ion-exchange resins with respect to Re. Initial studies involved strongly basic anion-exchange resins, which demonstrated excellent sorption selectivity for Re. However, the desorption of Re posed a challenge. The eluents used therein were expensive, and the process of obtaining high-purity ammonium perrhenate was complicated (Zhang et al., 2017). Therefore, existing technologies for Re recovery currently focus on weak-base (WB) anion-exchange resins. The processes performed with these resins use a solution of ammonium base as an eluent, which yields a high-purity ammonium perrhenate (Chanturiya et al., 2023; Xinke et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017).

In this context, WB anion-exchange resins are particularly important in the processing of secondary sources of Re. Various products possess these functionalities, among which *Purolite* plays a key role in Re-related industries. It offers a WB macroporous resin with two amine complexes, namely, Puromet MTA1701 (formerly Purolite A170/4675) and gel-type Puromet™ MTA1721 (formerly Purolite

A172/4635) (Purolite, n.d.). These resins are currently a part of ion-exchange technologies aimed at Re recovery; their functionalities have not been revealed owing to their technological importance.

Recently, another WB anion-exchange resin produced on an industrial scale was proposed by a Ukrainian manufacturer. The *AMB* ion-exchange resin is analogous to that offered by Purolite (Korovin et al., 2023; ‘Smoly’ Joint Stock Company.). Based on the literature and a few open repositories, several resins have been successfully applied to the selective separation of Re. They are based on: (i) poly(4-vinylpyridinevinylpyridine) (Jermakowicz-Bartkowiak and Kolarz, 2011) , (ii) methylimidazolium-functionalised Merrifield resin (Jia et al., 2013) , and (iii) those with functionalities derived from 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (Xiong et al., 2008) or 1-(3-aminopropyl)imidazole (Cyganowski et al., 2019a) . Further studies have proposed the applications of commercial resins such as ZS15 (Liu et al., 2018), ZS70 (Zhang et al., 2017), and Ambersep A920U (Zagorodnyaya et al., 2013). However, the industrial applicability of these materials has not been reported. Recently Zhang et al. (2020) conducted research on waste acid obtained from a copper smelter in China. They presented a direct ion-exchange method using a WB anion-exchange resin to recycle Re from waste acid during copper smelting. This technology has been implemented in Luoyang Molybden Industry Group, Jinduicheng Molybden Co., LTD, and China National Gold Group (Zhang et al., 2020). However, the resin structure was not disclosed therein.

Among recent technologies, the Institute of Non-Ferrous Metals (Gliwice, Poland) developed a Re recovery technology and implemented it in KGHM S.A. (Poland). Further, the proposed ion-exchange technology affords high-purity ammonium perrhenate from local Cu and Zn–Pb ores and from scrap. This technology extended the range of Re compounds produced in Poland *via* a novel methodology of producing high-purity HReO_4 and AgReO_4 and other compounds containing Co, Cu, Ni, and Li. These compounds in turn are further used in catalysis, aviation, and defence industries and in electromobility strategies, being a core material for supercapacitor production (Łukasiewicz Research Network — Institute of Non-Ferrous Metals) . However, the repositories do not provide any information on the ion-exchange resin used therein.

The review infers that WB anion-exchange resins constitute the core element of Re recovery technologies from various sources. However, owing to their significant industrial relevance, such resins have usually not been characterized and are unnamed in most cases. Limited reports provide some insights into the structures of WB functionalities that could be preferred for designing Re-selective anion-exchange resins. These studies function as extremely important guides because the currently applied materials have begun experiencing challenges associated with the depletion of Re sources (Shen et al., 2021; Wang and Wang, 2018; Xinke et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017). In this context, much more work must be done in this field.

6. Perspectives and industrial application outlook

The assessment of the areas of PGM recovery regarding their recent developments reveals that the most significant growth is achieved in the case of SX techniques, metal collection techniques, and

hydrometallurgical chloro-complexation, with a special focus on replacing HNO_3 by H_2O_2 as the oxidising agent. The pristine $\text{HCl-H}_2\text{O}_2$ aqueous solution (Ilyas et al., 2020; Paiva et al., 2022) or that enhanced by microwave radiation (Abo Atia et al., 2021) is an efficient and versatile leaching agent, allowing for the transfer of Pt, Pd, and Rh into the liquid phase at desirable efficiencies. However, this versatility also extends to other undesired elements (Abo Atia et al., 2021; Ilyas et al., 2020; Paiva et al., 2022), thereby necessitating further steps for extracting the PGMs.

Despite the change of the oxidiser, thereby minimising the emissions of harmful gases by eliminating the source of NO_x , Cl_2 , and HClO generated (Abo Atia et al., 2021; Ilyas et al., 2020; Kudryashov et al., 2004) together with a low-pH HCl solution remain strongly corrosive towards the equipment, imposing the use of the acid protection and the acidic waste mitigation efforts. Wastewater is a hindrance to these techniques, rendering difficulties in their transition to the industrial scale. For instance, at an L/S ratio of 2 (Paiva et al., 2022), 200 L of leaching solution is required per 100 kg of the secondary-source material, with some studies having examined L/S ratios of up to 80 (Suoranta et al., 2015), excluding the water used in the potential washing or pre-treatment steps.

Wastewater generation may be reduced via regeneration and recirculation of the aqueous liquors after the leaching step of a given batch of secondary-source material and the subsequent stripping of the PGMs. The desired elements could be extracted from the liquid phase using various methods described herein (see Section 3. Hydrometallurgy of PGM recovery), with either more (Chen et al., 2017; Firmansyah et al., 2019; Ilyas et al., 2022; Jafarifar et al., 2005) or less (Wiecka et al., 2022) selectivity. Then, it would be necessary to restore the original reagent concentrations, adjust the volume of the leaching liquor to any potential gain/loss, and recycle the leachate back to be used for another batch, with the unstripped ions still extant in the solution. Altogether, the stripping phase may also be eliminated, and the leach–regenerate–adjust steps could be repeated several times before selectively extracting the desired elements from a substantially more concentrated liquor. This technique would reduce the waste generation while reducing the processing time in a prospective industrial plant, thus allowing for a higher throughput.

Moreover, larger-scale recycling facilities belonging to major PGM refiners primarily pursue pyrometallurgical recovery routes, at the time of writing this review (Paiva et al., 2022; Yakoumis et al., 2021). However, some hydrometallurgical techniques are also being employed on an industrial scale (Crundwell et al., 2011; Devyatykh et al., 2018; Saguru et al., 2018), with new plants being established (IBC Advanced Technologies Inc., 2021). Additionally, the trend in the studies has departed from the pyrometallurgical pathways and shifted towards hydrometallurgy and other methods. Nevertheless, in regard to the PGM recovery from waste materials, hydrometallurgical techniques can be characterized as those in which the PGMs exist in an aqueous phase at some point—either the PGM source or a product of mass transfer from the PGM-bearing material—usually in the form of complex ions. While such solutions would be of use (Wei et al., 2022), subsequent recovery steps such as precipitation are typically required for obtaining the metal or its salt as an end-product (Paiva, 2017).

Depending on the extraction technique of choice, the desired element in the form of complex ions may just be selectively transferred into another phase, either solid or liquid, which can be regarded as recovery. Although ideas for application and further use of the resultant chemicals are typically not described in the papers introducing the given techniques, if the extraction is sufficiently selective, the products yielded therein could be harnessed as a half-product in subsequent chemical reactions and processing. Several researchers have explained the use of biometallurgical, ion-exchange, and adsorption techniques because they are ready-to-use and applied materials can function as catalysts (Akiba et al., 2022; Cyganowski et al., 2020, 2019b, 2018; Li et al., 2022; Song et al., 2022; Trucillo et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2022), consequently reducing the number of processing steps in a potential industrial application and greatly adding to their importance as future exploration pathways.

Hydrometallurgical PGM recovery techniques are regarded superior to pyrometallurgical techniques owing to less waste production and lower energy consumption, thus implying an enhanced ecological concern (Wiecka et al., 2022). The ability to capture elements from dilute streams, which is of significance in secondary-source processing, is gaining popularity. Moreover, IX and MRT possess this capability as well; hence, it is no longer unique to hydrometallurgical techniques (Cyganowski and Dzimitrowicz, 2020; Izatt et al., 2016; Wiecka et al., 2022).

Although strategies for PGM recovery have been studied extensively, and many suggestions for improvement have been presented in the literature, the scenario is complete different for Re recovery. Recovery of Re is a serious challenge because in numerous secondary sources, Re exists together with PGMs. Hence, the technologies applied to extracting and separating PGMs should preferably involve unit processes aimed at Re recovery. Existing technologies and most recent methodologies (Shen et al., 2021; Wang and Wang, 2018; Xinke et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017) are especially significant because despite their application to primary sources of Re, the process is recognized as recovery. Hence, technologies based on ion-exchange resins, which already playing their vital role in the industry, could be easily extended and applied to the processing of secondary sources of Re.

In this context, the approaches and methodologies applied for the extraction of Re from various matrices can be considered already well-functioning (John, 2015; Kesieme et al., 2019) as they enable effective production of Re-bearing solutions with ReO_4^- (Shen et al., 2021). The actual space for advancement is the application of solid ion-exchange materials for, especially those containing WB anion-exchange groups. To date, a few commercial materials are available, and designing and implementing novel materials will be a major challenge, based on further scientific reports (Shen et al., 2021; Xinke et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017). This issue will rapidly gain significance. Rhenium sources are depleting, which will further pose challenges to the capacity, selectivity, and susceptibility of the resins to contamination by various elements (Shen et al., 2021; Xinke et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017).

7. Summary

Efforts devoted to achieving sustainability involve designing, producing, and utilising various materials, among which transition-group metals play a crucial role. Platinum-group metals and Re are particularly relevant in this context as these rare metals are used together in a variety of technologies aimed at preserving the natural environment and increasing the energy efficiency. In this context, various catalytic materials and energy-efficient devices serve as a significant secondary source of PGMs and Re and are especially important, considering the seriously limited and depleting resources.

The topic of PGM and Re recovery from secondary sources is resilient, actively addressing the market trends and the responsible treatment of the environment. Further, the developed technologies apparently offer a great potential in persisting with the challenges, especially those related to the depleting resources of PGMs and Re. Thus, the single best industrialisable technology for PGM or Re recovery cannot be determined owing to the numerous factors involved therein—ecological concerns, economical and logistical aspects, and large dependence on the geographical location and local political situation. The best technique would possibly be a combination of currently used technologies from all areas of metallurgy of PGMs. However, the hydrometallurgical processes need to be focussed further, especially involving leaching strategies for PGM extraction and proper design of separation materials for Re recovery. A combination of these could result in the development of comprehensive technologies, potentially facilitating access to secondary sources of PGMs and Re, which ultimately could emerge as primary sources.

8. CRediT author statement

Sebastian Kinas: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation; **Dorota Jermakowicz-Bartkowiak:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Pawel Pohl, Anna Dzimitrowicz:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Piotr Cyganowski:** Conceptualisation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

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10. Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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